

Assessing unConventional Evidence (ACE) tool: development and content of a tool to assess the strengths and limitations of ‘unconventional’ source materials¹

Additional file 1: The ACE tool – detailed description and guidance for application

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¹ Please note that earlier versions of this tool were called the WEIRD (Ways of Evaluating Important and Relevant Data) tool and the END (Evaluating Non-conventional evidence) tool.

Additional file 1: The ACE tool – detailed description and guidance for application

Description of the document or source ²	
Authors	
Title	
Date of publication or access (if web-based)	
Publisher	
Place published or URL	
Language of publication	
ISBN	
DOI	
Type of source material	<p>Please select from the list below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Description of a programme or intervention or policy or reform (e.g., a health or welfare or environmental programme or intervention) <input type="checkbox"/> Description of the implementation of a programme or intervention or policy or reform <input type="checkbox"/> Description of a policy process or an aspect of this process <input type="checkbox"/> Commentary on a programme or intervention or policy or reform (e.g., a health systems or development sector policy or reform) <input type="checkbox"/> Other [please describe]:

Pre-assessment questions	
<p>Is the source material based on, or does it include, empirical data?³ <i>[This refers to information collected through measurement or observation, either quantitative or qualitative. Such data may include information from a Health Management Information System or a patient register that is not generated as part of a formal research process.]</i></p>	<p>If YES, then also include assessment criterion 6 highlighted in green below.</p>
<p>Assessment details</p>	<p>Name of assessor: Date of assessment:</p>

² In some instances, several sources may contribute to a description of a specific programme or a policy process. In these cases, you should look across all of the contributing sources when undertaking the ACE assessment.

³ Please see Table 2 in the ACE tool paper for a list of sources that include empirical data and could be assessed using the ACE tool.

ACE assessment criteria	Signaling questions for each criterion⁴	Applicability of each criterion	Assessment <i>Choose one of YES, NO, PARTIAL⁵, UNCLEAR or NOT APPLICABLE</i> <i>[The 'not applicable' option is relevant to questions 6 to 11]</i>	Justification for your assessment <i>[Include a justification for the assessment made, preferably supported by extracts (with page numbers) from the source material that is being assessed]</i>
1. Is the aim, objective or purpose for the source material described?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does the source material state its aim, objective or purpose clearly? In other words, for what purpose was the information gathered? <i>[For example, to describe a programme or policy reform]</i> If the aim, objective or purpose is not stated clearly by the authors, can it be derived from the material?⁶ 	Any kind of source materials		
2. Is the source of the information reported?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Are the sources (key informants, own experience, research study etc.) described? Where applicable, is there a clear description of who collected the information? 	Any kind of source materials		
3. Is there a description of the programme or intervention or policy or reform on which the	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Are the rationale, goals or objectives of the programme or intervention or policy or reform described?⁹ This may include the issues or gaps that the programme, intervention or policy aims to address 	Any kind of source materials that describe an intervention		

⁴ Not all of these signaling questions will be relevant for all types of source material and you should only apply those questions that are appropriate.

⁵ Select 'Partial' where some information is provided in relation to the assessment criterion but this information is not sufficient or not complete.

⁶ Where you have derived the aim or objective from the material, you should select 'Unclear' for your assessment.

⁹ This refers to the objectives of the programme or intervention or policy or reform described in the source material rather than the objective of the source material itself.

<p>source material focuses?^{7,8}</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is the content of the programme or intervention or policy described, including all of the important facets or elements? • Are the stakeholders or groups involved in delivering the programme or intervention or policy described, including their characteristics / background, skills or expertise, training and responsibilities? • Is the target/s of the programme or intervention or policy described? • Is a theory or change or logic model, that outlines how the programme or intervention or policy will work, described? • Are the methods used to implement the programme or intervention or policy, including the mode of delivery (e.g. face-to-face, via the internet), described? • Is any relevant training, described? • Are any materials used in the programme or intervention described? • Does the source material describe clearly any infrastructure and resources required for the programme or intervention or policy? • Does the source material describe when the programme or intervention or policy was started, when it finished, its intensity and whether there were any changes to the 	<p>or programme or policy</p>		
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⁷ A description of a programme or intervention or policy or reform may be the main focus of some source materials. Where that is the case, this question may overlap with question 6. In question 3, we are not looking at whether the description of the programme or intervention or policy or reform is sufficient to allow replication. Rather question 3 is concerned with whether sufficient information has been provided to allow users to understand what the programme or intervention or policy or reform is and how it was conceived and implemented.

⁸ For some kinds of interventions, additional tools are available that may provide useful signalling questions. These tools include the TIDieR checklist (1. Hoffmann TC, Glasziou PP, Boutron I, Milne R, Perera R, Moher D, Altman DG, Barbour V, Macdonald H, Johnston M *et al*: **Better reporting of interventions: template for intervention description and replication (TIDieR) checklist and guide**. *Bmj* 2014, **348**:g1687.) and the Consensus on Exercise Reporting Template (2. Slade SC, Dionne CE, Underwood M, Buchbinder R: **Consensus on Exercise Reporting Template (CERT): Explanation and Elaboration Statement**. *Br J Sports Med* 2016, **50**(23):1428-1437.)

	<p>programme or intervention or policy over time?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does the source material describe any mechanisms or monitoring used to ensure that the programme or intervention or policy or reform was implemented as intended (e.g., supervision and support of personnel, trainings, implementation checks, incentives)? 			
<p>4. Is there a description of the context/s to which the information described in the source material relates?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does the source material describe where the programme or policy or reform took place (e.g., country name(s), specific locations, urban/rural environments)? Does the source material describe clearly the context for the material, including (where relevant): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The setting (country, service, community) to which the description relates The system (e.g., health or welfare system), including the system level (e.g., frontline level) The historical, socio-cultural, socioeconomic or ethical context The political, legal, governance, policy and / or practice context, including relevant key events or policy initiatives? Does the source material describe clearly the stakeholders to which the description relates, including (where relevant): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The target population(s) or group(s) for the programme or intervention or policy Implementing organization(s) for the programme or intervention or policy Any other partners and stakeholders 	<p>Any kind of source materials</p>		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does the source material describe clearly how different stakeholders were involved in the programme or intervention or policy or reform? 			
5. Is the information complete?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does the source material describe any efforts to ensure that the information presented is complete and reliable? Does the information presented appear to be reasonably complete? <i>[For example, does the source report all of the elements / time periods outlined in the aim or objective?]</i> 	Source materials that include little or no empirical data		
6. Is the information accurate? ¹⁰	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does the source material have clearly stated methods, including (where relevant) the type of empirical study conducted and when the programme or intervention or policy was evaluated? Was the basis for selecting cases or people or clusters appropriate in relation to the question being addressed? Were the methods and tools for data collection appropriate in relation to the question being addressed? Were the data collectors appropriately trained and supported in their tasks? When were the data collected, and was the timespan of the data collection long enough to address the core issues fairly? Was the quality of the data collected monitored and was the quality shown to be adequate? 	Only source materials that include empirical data		

¹⁰ Note that whether the source material has clearly stated research aims or objectives is covered by assessment question 1 above. This question also draws on the risk of bias assessment described in 3. Gaitonde R, Oxman AD, Okebukola PO, Rada G: **Interventions to reduce corruption in the health sector**. *The Cochrane database of systematic reviews* 2016(8):CD008856.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is the method of analysis reported clearly? Is the method of analysis appropriate in relation to the question being addressed? • Is there a clear description of the outcome/s measured (where relevant)? • Is the outcome measure reliable (where relevant)? • Were these outcomes measured appropriately (where relevant)? • Do these outcomes provide a reasonable assessment of the issue being considered (where relevant)? 			
7. Is the information representative?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the information is drawn from a sample of the population of interest, is there a clear description of how the sampling was conducted? • Was the sampling approach appropriate (where applicable)? • If generalisations were made to wider population(s) or setting(s), is there a rationale for doing so and a description of how this was done? • Were any generalisations made informed by the populations, settings or other contextual aspects covered by the source material? In other words, do the generalisations made appear to be appropriate? 	Any kind of source materials, but may be more relevant to sources that include empirical data		
8. Is information provided to support any findings or conclusions made?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are the findings or conclusions (where applicable) supported by relevant information? <i>[For example, does the source material make transparent the linkages between the data that were reported and any inferences or conclusions made? Are citations provided for information from elsewhere?]</i> • Are the findings or conclusions reasonable, in relation to the information presented? 	Any kind of source materials		

9. Are any limitations of the information and / or methods discussed in the source material?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does the source material outline any gaps in the information provided? • Does the source material outline any weaknesses of the information provided? 	Any kind of source materials		
10. Are relevant rights and ethics considerations described?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does the source material discuss relevant rights and ethics considerations? • Does the source material indicate whether ethics approval was sought and obtained? • Does the source material report how consent to provide data or information was obtained? 	Any kind of source materials		
11. Are any interests declared and any potential conflicts of interest noted?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does the source material indicate if any of the authors are affiliated with the organization or entity whose programme or intervention or policy is described? • Is the source of funding for developing the material reported? • Does the source material indicate if any of the authors are affiliated with the organization or entity that has funded the programme or policy described <i>[For example, a governmental department or the private sector]</i>? • Are any potential conflicts of interest described? • Do the authors indicate how any potential conflicts of interest were addressed?¹¹ • Do the authors discuss how their own backgrounds and / or perspectives may have influenced the research questions and process? 	Any kind of source materials		

¹¹ If important potential conflicts of interest have not been addressed adequately in the source material, the response option 'No' or 'Partial' should be selected for this criterion.

Overall assessment of the limitations of the source material ¹²	Explanation of overall assessment
<p><i>Please choose one of:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>no or very minor concerns</i> • <i>minor concerns</i> • <i>moderate concerns</i> • <i>serious concerns</i> 	

Key sources include: the SUPPORT Tools for Evidence-informed Policymaking (STP) series [4], McGrath 2006 [5], the TIDieR checklist [1] and the AACODS checklist [6, 7].

¹² In making an overall assessment of the limitations of the source material, you should consider whether the concerns you have identified by applying the questions above might undermine the reliability or trustworthiness of the material. You should look across your responses to all of the questions in the tool to identify these concerns. ‘No or very minor concerns’ should be selected when the answer to most questions in the tool is YES. ‘Minor concerns’ should be chosen when the answer to many questions in the tool is YES and only a few questions are assessed as PARTIAL or UNCLEAR. If you think that the concerns you have identified would undermine or would probably undermine, the reliability of the material, then you may want to select ‘moderate’ or ‘serious’ concerns.

A weighting has not been assigned to each question as the importance of each question may vary by type of source material. Also, it is not recommended to attempt to numerically score ACE assessments as this may give a false sense of precision. ACE assessments are judgements, and the tool aims is to make these as explicit and transparent as possible through providing an explanation of the assessment made.

References

1. Hoffmann TC, Glasziou PP, Boutron I, Milne R, Perera R, Moher D, Altman DG, Barbour V, Macdonald H, Johnston M *et al*: **Better reporting of interventions: template for intervention description and replication (TIDieR) checklist and guide**. *Bmj* 2014, **348**:g1687.
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4. Lavis JN, Oxman AD, Lewin S, Fretheim A: **SUPPORT Tools for evidence-informed health Policymaking (STP)**. *Health research policy and systems / BioMed Central* 2009, **7 Suppl 1**:11.
5. McGrath Y, Sumnall H, Edmonds K, McVeigh J, Bellis M: **Review of grey literature on drug prevention among young people**. London, UK: National Institute for Health and Clinical Excellence (NICE); 2006. Available at <http://www.dldocs.stir.ac.uk/documents/nice.greylit.pdf>.
6. NICE: **Interim methods guide for developing service guidance**. Manchester, UK: National Institute for Health and Care Excellence; 2014. Available at: <https://www.nice.org.uk/process/pmg8/chapter/introduction>.
7. Tyndall J: **AACODS (Authority, Accuracy, Coverage, Objectivity, Date, Significance) Checklist**. Flinders, Australia: Flinders University; 2010. Available at: https://dspace.flinders.edu.au/jspui/bitstream/2328/3326/4/AACODS_Checklist.pdf.